

Tropical peat artificial compaction?

Soil compaction refers to incremental increase of bulk density as a result of macro pores reduction from either single or multidirectional loads. Adapting the theory of tropical peat soil compaction processes, there are two main forces that induce peat compaction. Namely, external and internal forces. External load is a static and dynamic load that derives from the lateral forces to the soil surface, while internal load refers to the process that occurs due to alteration of soil physical changed by water suction gradient. In general, compaction in peat can occur with or without peat oxygen availability (i.e. aerobic and anaerobic) at peat horizons that are divided into three main components (see Fig. 1), which I called “The triple-C”. The first component (C1) is a combination of compaction and shrinkage, which is considered as an entity of peat subsidence in the aerobic layer beside peat oxidation that can increase the bulk density value. At the unsaturated soil peat layer (aerobic layer), the induced loads may be immediate or temporary. The impact on the peat surface could be caused by several factors, such as heavy machinery wheels, rainfall drops, and animal tracks. The second and third components are associated within anaerobic layer at saturated peat (anoxic horizon), which are described as primary and secondary consolidation. The primary consolidation (C2) is induced by rapid decrease of moisture regime, whereas the secondary consolidation (C3) is linked with resistance of peat materials to compaction. Since soil consolidation is affected within the saturated soil peat layer or anaerobic horizon, the load is applicable over a longer time period and continuous, for example, over a wetting and drying cycle or with long-term water table fluctuation.

In literature review on the terminology of peat compaction. I mentioned the need for a critical level of understanding of tropical peat compaction due to the coupled processes between oxidative, consolidation, and shrinkage and man-made compaction (also known as artificial compaction). By defi-

Tropical peat subsidence mechanisms or compaction illustrated by

Samuel, M. K (2020).

nitiation, compaction comprises two coupled elements, compression and consolidation, whereby compression refers to the reduction of material due to the displacement of the oxic phase, and consolidation refers to the increase in mechanical strength of the material due to particle-to-particle interaction resulting from the collapse of peat soil under its own weight. In contrast, the compressibility of peat soil does not make it easy to conduct direct measurements because of the different interrelated parameters such as peat depth, maturity, and bulk density. Most present works that have focused on artificial compaction and peat soil have only considered peat from the context of a soil conditioning agent and an additive for mineral soils due to the 99% organic matter content. Hence, this type of peat soil has a compressibility level of 300% to 400% and a far greater capacity to return to its original condition – unless the hydrophobicity characteristic is achieved. Yet grouping subsidence and compaction (i.e. shrinkage, compression, and consolidation) together has led to some confusion. The application of tropical peatland compaction as a subsidence index has increased. For example, peat subsidence has been used as a measurable indicator to determine carbon loss by observing changes to peat depth. In contrast, I argued that the compaction process of natural peat ecosystems does not always represent peat subsidence. This is because of incompressible layers that dominate peat subsurface, that compaction does not always mean peat loss and the fact that the peat expands and contracts in response to water table fluctuation level due to high porosity and buoyancy characteristics, also independently of carbon loss. As such, data on peat subsidence and surface level growth is heavily depend on water table level and should not be interpreted as a measure of carbon loss without being corrected against soil bulk density.

The complexity underlying compaction magnitude is derived from several factors, such as abiotic, biotic, and anthropogenic factors (man-made/artificial compaction). Nevertheless, the combination of compaction and shrinkage as an entity seems very difficult to distinguish. Most literature works defined tropical peat compaction based on the nature of the study site. For instance, in logged-over or drained forest ecosystems, peat compaction source is always described as a result from water table fluctuation between seasonal variations that causes shrinkage (bulk density increase), or oxidation (by microbial activity), which decreases bulk density. As for developed peatland ecosystems, such as agri-systems, most of the authors described peat compaction as a coupled process caused by heavy machinery or shrinkage by drainage, which contribute to increased bulk density. This particular landscape-based definition leads to confusion towards the clarity definition mechanism of compaction on tropical peatland among researchers. Therefore, in order to better understand the terminology of 'peat compaction', research should be initiated to separate the first component (C1) from oxidation and C loss effects, but rather, considers compaction caused by heavy machinery and shrinkage as a single entity. So, what do you think? 'Yay' or 'nay' to the existence of active peat compaction?

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